

THE ROLE OF JUDGE IN CIVIL PROCEDURE OF UZBEKISTAN

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One of the central problems in civil procedure is clarifying the actual roles and responsibilities of the judges and the parties (lawyers) in the conduct of a civil dispute. To solve this problem, the Code of Civil Procedure establishes certain principles, which define the image of the court. One of the most important principles of civil process is the adversarial proceedings principle. This principle characterizes the civil process from its beginning in the trial in the court of first instance, in the court of appeal, until its conclusion in the Supreme Court.

The adversarial proceedings principle determines the limits of the actions of the judge and the parties in civil proceedings. It helps to ensure the fulfillment of tasks of civil proceedings, which the correct, timely consideration and resolution of civil cases.

There is a classic division of two large systems according to the role of the judge and the parties:

- 1) Adversarial system (Verhandlungsmaxime);
- 2) Inquisitorial system (Inquisitionsgrundsatz order-maxime) [1].

In both systems, the civil process is focused on the task of solving a conflict between two parties whose interests are in confront each other. But it differs from each other in a number of aspects, depending on the order in which this process is carried out.

According article 10 of CCP (Code of Civil Procedure) of Uzbekistan, civil proceedings shall be conducted on the basis of adversarial nature and equality of arms [2].

Its content is described by scholars as follows. First of all, any person participating in the case can apply for a civil case, make statements, raise objections, make requests, prove his right by submitting evidence to the court, express his opinion on the content of the case; secondly, the prosecutor can prove the circumstances of the case, give his opinion to the court on some issues of the case, as well as on all cases; thirdly, the court has the right to collect evidence on its own initiative in order to determine the truth by an objective method [3].

The principle of adversary means that the persons participating in this case should present their demands and objections before the court by proving the circumstances that are important for the case, participate in all procedural actions and have their own opinion on all the issues that need to be resolved. It

is a set of rights and obligations in expressing opinions, as well as actively assisting the court in determining the circumstances of the case and collecting relevant evidence [4].

The adversarial principle determines the activeness of the parties participating in the case in proving their claims and objections, the procedure for their preparation of case materials, increases the role of the court in the process, and thereby ensures that the court makes a legal, reasonable and fair decision. The essence of the adversarial principle is that in civil proceedings, the parties are opposed to each other in terms of their interests, and the discussion of cases in court is conducted on the basis of resolving the disputed issue between them [5]. The adversarial principle consists mainly of presenting evidence and giving an objection (explanation, opinion), which guarantees the active participation of the parties and other persons involved in the case in court [6].

According to the classical definition recognized globally, litigation based on the adversarial principle carried out on the basis of opposition, equality and their activity of both parties, in which the court takes an inactive position. The essence of this principle is precisely that the parties stand in front of the court and try to convince the judge with the help of the various evidences they present on the disputed issue, and the burden of proof rests with the parties. As a general rule, the court should be excluded from collecting evidence and should perform the task of an impartial assessor.

It is necessary to maintain the active participation of the judge as a special procedure for certain categories of cases, taking into account their specific aspects and difficulties in gathering (proving) evidence. For example, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 29, 2022 "On measures to ensure the effective protection of the rights of citizens and business entities in relations with state bodies and to further increase the public's trust in the courts" decision to conduct administrative court proceedings based on the principle of "active participation of the court", in which administrative courts are obliged to collect evidence on their own initiative to determine the true circumstances of the case, and the citizen or business entity whose rights have been violated. It is known that it is relatively difficult to ensure the equality of the parties in this category of cases, because all the evidence can be found in state bodies [7].

Although it is stated in Article 10 of the CCP of Uzbekistan that the conduct of civil process is carried out on the basis of the adversarial principle, this norm does not clearly indicate the essence of the principle of dispute. In order to fully

ensure the adversarial principle, it is necessary to clearly define its content first. The experience of developed foreign countries plays an important role in this. As is well known, Japan is today a highly industrialized modern country. Civil procedural law of Japan has gradually moved from an inquisitorial system to an adversarial system. It can be said that Japan has a civil procedural law that aims to embody the effective aspects and elements of the two classical systems above. Therefore, there are many lessons to be learned from this experience.

Modern Japanese civil procedure system was first modelled in the last century after the German law and underwent a reform after the Second World War under a strong American influence. Therefore, the present Japanese procedural system is hybrid. It has a predominantly German side, and a significant American side. Most recently, Japan has experienced significant civil procedure reform by a new Code of Civil Procedure of 1996 and further amendments to it in 2003.

In Japanese civil procedure, the division of roles of a judge and litigants is generally clarified as follows: the judge plays a central role in conducting procedures and directing oral arguments, and litigants play critical roles in asserting facts and producing evidence. It is the judge who decides the dates of oral hearings, examination of witnesses, and rendition of judgment (Article 93 of CCP). The judge also decides whether evidence should be examined (Article 181 of CCP). The judgement should not be based on facts that litigants do not assert or evidence that they do not submit in court (Verhandlungsmaxime in Germany).

Regardless of such a division of roles, the Code of Civil Procedure also promotes cooperation between judges and litigants in order to realise effective justice. For instance, a judge is allowed to ask litigants to clarify their allegations so as to clarify legal and factual matters if these are unclear to him/her. Furthermore, a judge may ask litigants to submit evidence if they have not (Article 149 of CCP). A judge is also allowed to make some dispositions to clarify legal and factual matters, such as asking litigants to submit documents or examining expert witnesses (Article 151 of CCP). On the other hand, litigants are allowed to object to a judge's directions or to ask a judge to give some orders or directions (Article 150 of CCP). After the reform of the Code of Civil Procedure in 1996, a judge also may ask for litigants' opinions regarding their choice of preparatory procedure and order of examination of witnesses or litigants. Thus, judges and litigants are expected to cooperate with each other in conducting procedure and finding facts [8].

According to the adversarial principle of Japan, judges should ensure the case only within the evidence gathered by the parties, and according to the circumstances of the case, and make a decision in accordance with those evidence. Thus, in court proceedings on civil cases, the court should determine the truth based on the evidence and facts presented by the parties. Each party must disclose to the court and the other party the evidence substantiating its claims, objections and other arguments.

The role of the court in advancing the case, under the CCP, is to preserve the fairness and procedure of the adversarial process. Judges:

- Assist a party in obtaining evidence.
- Appoint an expert.
- Check documents and evidence.
- Verify the justifiability of the arguments of the parties and the reliability of the submitted evidence.

The court cannot collect evidence and documents on its own initiative.

A party to the litigation can apply to a judge with a request to claim evidence from a counterparty or other parties specifying the details of this evidence and how this evidence may impact outcome of the litigation. In this case the judge issues a written request to provide certain documents, setting deadlines to be followed. Failure to execute the court's request in theory results in administrative liability, however, in practice, this mechanism does not work effectively. The parties usually submit original written documents. A court may also accept copies of written documents, unless the other party challenges their content. A party is not obliged to disclose documents that are helpful for its opponent.

The adversarial principle is one of the important principles of civil process, and strengthening the practical implementation of this principle is one of the main goals of the reforms implemented in the field of judiciary in our country. Strengthening the comprehensive implementation of this principle is also in the second direction of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, called "Priority directions for ensuring the rule of law and further reforming the judicial system" [9].

As a logical continuation of these reforms, and as the second direction of the new Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, it was emphasized that in order to achieve justice and the rule of law, it is necessary to realize the principles of real equality and adversary of the parties in court proceedings [10].

It can be proposed to define the content of adversarial principle and equality of rights of the parties as follows.

Civil proceedings shall be carried out based on the adversarial principle and equality of rights of the parties. In the course of civil proceedings, the parties shall choose their standpoint, ways and means for defending thereof independently and irrespective of court and other persons participating in the case.

The court, while maintaining objectivity and impartiality, shall manage the process, shall create the necessary conditions for the parties to exercise their procedural rights to a full and objective examination of the circumstances of the case. The court shall explain to the entities participating in the case their rights and obligations, warn about the consequences of committing or not performing procedural actions, clarify their legal positions and arguments, discuss the circumstances of the case with them and, in the cases provided for by the law, assist them in exercising their rights. The court shall base its decision only on the evidence, participation in the study of which was ensured on equal grounds for each party.

The court, on a reasoned petition of a party shall take measures to collect and study the case materials, verify the validity of the arguments of the parties and the reliability of the evidence provided to the court, as well as perform other actions aimed at achieving the objectives of civil proceedings. The court shall show equal and respectful attitude towards the parties.

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